

An SDOM Approach to Reactive Audio

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ABSTRACT

The static DOM, or SDOM, approach to building web frameworks was first articulated by Phil Freeman[3] as an alternative to the virtual DOM, or VDOM[8], approach used by frameworks like ReactJS[11] and Vue[13]. Since then, several projects, most notably SolidJS[2], have developed SDOM and related ideas into industry-grade web frameworks. This paper explores the applicability of the SDOM approach to Web Audio. It starts by defining the main concepts behind SDOM, including functional reactive programming[12] (FRP) and the incremental lambda calculus[1]. It then discusses some of the unique challenges in porting SDOM to Web Audio, including one-to-many relationships, feedback loops, referential transparency, and live-coding. After proposing solutions to these problems, it presents benchmarks of the SDOM-based approach compared to Tone.js, an imperative library for web audio.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the creation of AngularJS[4] in 2010, web frameworks have attempted with varying degrees of success to provide a declarative, performant, and reactive approach to building web applications. These three goals are each trade-offs with respect to each other, and frameworks that excel in two must find novel solutions to achieve the third.

- The most declarative and performant structure possible is immutable HTML, which is by definition not reactive.
- Declarative and reactive applications use a virtual DOM, or “VDOM”, which has poor performance as it requires frequent diffing over large data structures.
- Performant and reactive applications tend to funnel information to a web app directly from event listeners, which is naturally fragmented and resists the declarative style.

In 2018, Phil Freeman, the creator of the PureScript language, proposed a new approach to building web applications that started from the declarative+performant position

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and attempted to bring its reactivity in line with declarative+reactive frameworks like React and Vue. This approach is known as the static DOM, or SDOM, approach[3]. The motivating insight behind the SDOM approach is that most websites’ structures change infrequently, if at all. Freeman writes:

Denotationally speaking, the virtual DOM is very appealing, but operationally, it is a heavy-weight solution for many problems. Every time we modify our application state and rerun our render function, we allocate a new tree of (virtual) DOM components, and perform a tree diff in order to discover what must change in the actual DOM. For many (most?) applications, this seems to be overkill. We can optimize the diff algorithm in various ways, but ultimately, the diffing is essentially unnecessary — for simple changes to the model, I know precisely which nodes need to be updated. We simply need a way to make this obvious in the code.

He goes on to argue that layout primitives of CSS3 such as display, flex and grid make it possible to build a web application where all of the nodes are rendered during an initial render, and they are displayed and moved based on user interactions. Even dynamic structures like lists can, to an extent, be modeled by rendering a reasonable upper limit of elements and then displaying or hiding them as necessary. For applications that fall into this category, he proposes the SDOM method.

1.1 Defining SDOM

The SDOM approach is one where each element of a DOM is subscribed to an event listener, and values are broadcast to the events in order to change the elements’ attributes. For example, in the DOM snippet below:

```
<div style="background-color: red;">
  <h1 id="hi">Hello</h1>
  <p>The SDOM is:</p>
  <ul>
    <li style="margin:3px;">Dynamic</li>
    <li>Performant</li>
    <li>Reactive</li>
  </ul>
</div>
```

The DOM elements (the section, h1, p, ul, and three li-s) never change. Each attribute that is present, such as the

style of the section and list item or the id of the header, is subscribed to an event listener and updates when a new event fires.

1.2 SDOM in the declarative / performant / reactive trifecta

The next three sections will explore how the SDOM fares as a declarative, performant and reactive framework for building web apps.

1.2.1 Declarative

By keeping the DOM static, one is able to declare its content once. This means that no intermediary representations are needed for diffing, which allows one to use what is called a final encoding. In final encodings, functions are used to immediately transform input into its final representation without passing through an intermediary algebraic data type, or ADT. In many cases, this means that a rendering engine can simply accept a string with HTML inside of it and use it to set the innerHTML property of a DOM Node.

1.2.2 Performant

Because the declarative content of the SDOM is rendered once using a final encoding, it is extremely efficient: it avoids the needless allocation of resources used in an intermediary representation. When using strings for innerHTML, the browser can often parse and render a DOM string with sub-millisecond performance. These strings can be verified for correctness at compile time using a tool like the webpack JSX compiler or type-level string validation in languages like Haskell, Idris and PureScript. Furthermore, as the rendering only happens once upon initial render, changes to the DOM have do not require diffing or re-rendering nodes themselves, which leads to significant performance gains over VDOM frameworks like React.

1.2.3 Reactive

SDOM web apps that follow Freeman's original design are reactive with the major caveat that the nodes themselves cannot change (we will loosen this restriction later when discussing incremental functions). The individual nodes, then, are subscribed to event listeners, which funnel DOM events like clicks and timers down to the nodes. The restriction that the DOM must be static is what allows this event-based approach to work. Without a static DOM, elements could be removed and added at-will, and there would be no certainty that an event would reach its destination. This would make web apps very extremely fragile, as the presence or absence of nodes could not be guaranteed. For example, an NFT service that relies on the delivery of a digital asset to a buyer could not be certain that the node in which the asset is displayed is actually present. The static nature of the DOM solves this problem

1.3 Functional reactive programming

When implemented poorly, the SDOM approach has the potential to inherit the same performance limitations of VDOM: instead of traversing a large arboreal data structure to construct a diff, one winds up traversing a large arboreal data structure to dispatch an event to all of the nodes that may need it. Functional reactive programming[12], or FRP, is a way to solve this problem. By performing automatic memoization and providing map-reduce algorithms

for time-series data, functional reactive programming eliminates redundant computations. There is an emerging body of literature on functional-reactive programming as applied to web programming, audio and specifically Web Audio[9] to which the reader can refer for more definitions of fundamental FRP primitives.

Another important aspect of FRP is its ability to preserve state. It can do this in three ways:

- The Behavior type can be used by an event to poll the state of an external entity, like a random-number generator or whether report, when the event is fired.
- The fold operation can be used to update an initial state whenever an event is fired. This is the cornerstone operation of The Elm Architecture.
- The fix combinator is used to feed event data back into itself. When done properly, fix can be used to model differential equations and debouncing.

Because state can be added ad-hoc at any point in the event chain, it adds a powerful mechanism to localize state to only the nodes in an SDOM that need it.

1.4 Incremental functions

The most severe limitation of the SDOM approach is its handling of dynamic content. There are two cases where this is particularly problematic:

- For some services, it is impractical or inefficient to allocate an upper-bound of resources. Event with techniques like DOM recycling for infinite scroll, a large DOM tree can cause low-end mobile devices to perform poorly, even when very few elements are updated.
- Some content, such as that produced by markdown parsers, can only be denoted in terms of recursive combinators. This includes:
 - lists
 - * within lists.

This requires the layout framework itself to be Turing complete, which cannot be achieved by the SDOM approach as presented thus far. One solution to this problem is the incremental lambda calculus[1], which requires functions to be expressed as a series of diffs applied to a base data structure. For example, when working with a HashMap, the primitives of the incremental lambda calculus only allow inserting, deleting and modifying elements at indices, but one does not have access to the map as a whole. Incremental approaches have proved effective in modeling dynamic structures in otherwise immutable systems, such as mapping-s in Ethereum's Solidity language.

Applying the incremental lambda calculus to SDOM, one can use an indexed hash map to create and destroy internal SDOMs that have their own event logic and subscribers. This adds the overhead of keeping track of what indices are present and which ones are absent, but this can be accomplished by the fold and fix primitives mentioned in the last section and can be accomplished in $O(1)$ amortized time when using an efficient hash map implementation.

1.5 SDOM in industry

The SDOM approach was first articulated by Phil Freeman in 2018. Separate from Freeman’s work, the first industry-grade SDOM framework, SolidJS[2], began in late 2018 and, as of the writing of this article in April 2022, is the most popular and one of the most performant SDOM frameworks. Other frameworks that occupy the declarative+performant area of the web-framework trifecta, like Svelte and Hugo, have incorporated ideas from the SDOM approach into their implementations as well.

2. SDOM AND WEB AUDIO

At first glance, the SDOM approach seems ideally suited to web audio. Audio graphs change relatively infrequently, their nodes respond to events, and the nodes themselves are not referentially transparent. In applications that need dynamic and recursively-defined content, incremental functions over indexed structures can be used to update the audio graph. However, there are four main issues that exist in web audio that are not addressed by the SDOM approach:

- One-to-many relationships.
- Feedback loops.
- Leaking referentially-opaque nodes.
- Live-coding and other dynamic arts.

The following section proposes solutions to all four issues. It does so in JavaScript pseudocode, occasionally employing TypeScript-esque syntax when explicit types are necessary.

2.1 One-to-many relationships

In the DOM, a node can only ever have one parent. In Web Audio, however, a node can be connected to many outgoing nodes as an audio or control signal. One way to articulate this relationship in the SDOM style is to use a fan operation that injects an opaque blob into a closure where it can be used 0 or more times.

```
var node =
  fan(sawtoothOsc(440.0), (osc) =>
    gain(bandpass(1000.0, osc)
      , highpass(3000.0, osc)))
```

In the example above, `osc` is injected into the function at the moment of interpretation. This makes it possible to use in a purely-functional context that expects referential transparency: as there is no way to construct the node aside from its opaque representation, it is the equivalent of a unary constructor like `Unit` in Haskell, Scala and PureScript.

2.2 Feedback

Feedback in an SDOM Web Audio representation can be handled in the same manner that it is in FRP: via a fixed-point combinator.

```
var node =
  fix((node) =>
    gain(sinOsc(440.0)
      , highpass(1000.0, delay(0.2, node))))
```

As with `fan`, `fix` is an opaque blob that is provided by the interpreting library at the moment of function evaluation. An issue arises in attributing unique IDs to the recursively-defined node, as the ID attributed to the return value will also have to be attributed to the input node. This is a classic problem when working with De Bruijn indices, and it can be solved by a deferred naming strategy: if an audio node in the underlying engine is defined as `(id) => node`, then the same ID can be given to the input and output nodes once the function has been evaluated.

```
var fix = (f) => {
  var id = Math.random();
  var i = mkNode(id);
  var out = f(i);
  return out(id);
}
```

A problem still exists with the connecting of nodes in a final encoding, as certain nodes will not yet be created at the moment of connection, but it is possible for the final encoding to defer the connection of nodes until both ends of the connection have been created.

2.3 Referential transparency

Up until now, we have avoided running into issues of referential transparency because the only values that are not referentially transparent in our SDOM Web Audio implementation, namely the inputs to `fan` and `fix`, are singletons, which along with nullary values (ie `Void` in Haskell) have identical representations in opaque and transparent context, as they can only be substituted for themselves.

This issue is problematic, however, for nodes that emit events, such as `AudioBufferSourceNode` and `OscillatorNode`, both of which emit an ended event. Imagine the following scenario:

```
var node =
  fix((node) =>
    gain(sinOsc(myFreq
      , ended(() => push(node)()))));
```

In the `sinOsc`’s event listener for the ended event, we have now pushed a referentially opaque reference to a gain node. This reference can be consumed by any event subscription and can be used, for example, in another audio graph’s definition. As the other audio graph belongs to a different context, it would break at the moment of instantiation.

The solution to this problem is to use existential typing to “lock” nodes into a context. Existential types[7], or rank-N types, are a zero-cost abstraction that establishes a closed computational context in strongly-typed languages. In dynamically-typed languages like JavaScript this is impossible, so we’ll use TypeScript pseudocode to express this idea.

```
type Node<A> = {
  id: number;
}
type Run =
  (node: <A>( : Node<A>) => Audio)
  => Audio
```

Now, all nodes passed to `Run` must be polymorphic over a phantom type `A`, which means that it cannot be specialized:

it needs to remain universally quantified. Trying to pass in a node from another context will not work because it will, by definition, be specialized to the scope of the universal quantifier from another context. This is also called a Skolem variable escaping its scope and occurs when a quantified variable from a statement in Skolem-normal form[5] is used in another statement. For example, if you say “All Z like treats” and “All Z like to play” and agree that Z is not a concrete type but a variable to be determined later, the two Z’s cannot be mutually interchanged because their scopes are different and they could wind up being instantiated with different entities.

This technique of using existential quantification to create a closed computational context is most commonly used in the ST monad from Haskell[10] and PureScript, which uses a similar approach to create type-safe mutable references.

2.4 Live coding

As mentioned before, incremental functions provide a way to inject dynamic behavior into an SDOM approach, and the same technique can be used for an SDOM-ified Web Audio. However, the functions fan and fix result in a situation where the nodes used therein are hermetically sealed within their closures. That means that if, for example, one is performing a live-coding set, it is impossible to connect a node from closure A to closure B, whereas in an imperative-style language like SuperCollider this is not a problem.

The solution to this problem is to create a referentially opaque node that is itself an event and to attach a selfEvent to every node that, when triggered, pushes a reference to the node to enclosing event. Every time a new node is supplied to the event, the previous node (if there was one) is disconnected and the new node is connected.

```
var node =
  event((node, push) =>
    gain(sinOsc(440.0
      , selfEvent(push)
      , ended(() => push(node)))));
```

3. BENCHMARKS

To benchmark the SDOM approach to Web Audio, I used purescript-ocarina¹, a PureScript Web Audio library designed using SDOM principles, and Tone.js[6]². Tone.js occupies the performant+reactive part of the DOM trifecta at the expense of not being declarative.

3.1 Benchmark design

As ocarina’s design decisions occupy the declarative+performant part of the design space and uses the SDOM design pattern to achieve high reactivity, it was important to design a highly reactive experiment. As such, in this experiment, I created an event every 0.25 seconds that triggered 90 reactive events (turning on an oscillator, triggering an ADSR envelope, and turning off an oscillator) in both frameworks to stress test reactivity.

3.2 Tone.js

Note that, in Tone.js, an ADSR envelope is used by default, so it is not specified in the example below.

¹<https://wac2022-sdom.surge.sh/wags.html>

²<https://wac2022-sdom.surge.sh/tone.html>

Figure 1: Tone.js Benchmark Results

Figure 2: PureScript Ocarina Benchmark Results

```
const n = 30;
const gainNodes =
  Array.from(Array(n).keys())
    .map(()=>newTone.Gain(0.002)
      .toDestination());
const oscs=
  Array.from(Array(n).keys())
    .map((i)=>
      newTone.Oscillator(440.0+i*80)
        .connect(gainNodes[i]));
Tone.Transport.scheduleRepeat((time)=>{
  for(var i=0;i<n;i++) {
    oscs[i].start(time).stop(time+0.1);
  }
}, "8n");
Tone.Transport.start();
```

3.3 PureScript Ocarina

```
music time=do
let
  e0=adsr<<<add 0.03
  oon=bangOn'
  oof=bangOff'<<<add 0.22
  [gain1.0
  (map(\i->gain 0.0 (map e0 time)
    [sinOsc(toNumber i*80.0+440.0)
    (keepLatest$map(oneOf
    <$>sequence[oon,oof]))time])]
  (0..29))
  ]
myIv1<-memoize
  $ interval ctx 0.25
  $ bang 0.25
run2 ctx (music myIv1)
```

3.4 Benchmark results

The benchmarking was run 10 times over roughly 10 second intervals. Ocarina occupies on average 1.37 This shows that Ocarina, coming from a position of being performant and declarative, is able to achieve high reactivity in a reasonable number of lines of code and excellent performance.

Figure 3: Tone.js call stack for a single ictus on top, ocarina on the bottom.

The main cause of the discrepancy between the results is the globally-controlled scheduling in Tone.js versus the event-based scheduling in Ocarina. Because each node adds and removes itself, Ocarina has a flurry of smaller function calls with a limited number of global functions in the stack space. Tone, on the other hand, uses a global scheduling algorithm (the audio equivalent of VDOM) that results in approximately twelve functions like `forEachTickBetween` spanning a long time-frame on the stack.

In addition to these long running processes, Tone.js has a much deeper call stack with many redundant calls. While this is not a necessary consequence of the VDOM approach, it is an easy vice to fall into. If scheduling functions are idempotent (which they are in Tone.js), certain patterns can result in spurious traversals. The SDOM approach, by design, protects against this with unsubsubscription: in case of an accidental re-firing of a computation, unscheduled nodes do not receive any events, and the operation is a no-op that consumes almost no computation time.

4. CONCLUSION

In this article, the SDOM approach of web application development was presented and applied to the Web Audio domain. In doing so, the article proposed solutions to several shortcomings of the SDOM approach and provided benchmarks against an industry leading framework, Tone.js. The SDOM approach opens up entire categories of reactive applications that are difficult or impossible with heavier scheduling algorithms. For example, <https://joyride.netlify.app> is implemented with an SDOM audio engine, freeing up compute cycles for the heavy graphical rendering while still achieving sub-fifteen-millisecond reactive audio.

Further avenues of research can explore applying this approach to the DSP graph itself as well as using nested and recursively-defined events to create more dynamic and expressive audio graphs.

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